

Animating Tangible Narratives:

Creative Application of Animation and Interactive Technologies for Playful Interactions in the exhibition of Ceramic Stories [digital connections]

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ABSTRACT

This paper explores the creative application of animation and interactive technologies to craft playful, tangible interactions that convey imaginative stories and enhance spectator experiences in the exhibition "Ceramic Stories [digital connections]" at the Australian Design Centre. It demonstrates the process of creating digital connections between artifacts and audiences, based on the imaginative and historical narratives collaborating with two ceramic artists, Sebastian Conti and Casey Chen and their series of work in distinct. This illustrates the process of establishing digital linkages between artefacts and audiences. The study suggests the use of interactive technologies and animation to change spectator experiences and increase audience participation by drawing on this experience.

CCS CONCEPTS

• Playful Interactions and Experiences • Generative Art • AR

KEYWORDS

Playful Interaction, Interactive, Animation, Interactive technologies, Augmented Reality (AR), Digital Connections, Max MSP

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1 INTRODUCTION

The traditional gallery experience of artifacts often limits audience engagement, reducing the rich histories and narratives of these items to static displays. Interactive technologies, and digital storytelling have been shown to enhance the audience's connection with cultural artifacts by making the experiences more immersive and engaging [1].

The exhibition "Ceramic Stories [Digital Connections]" aimed to showcase Australia's distinctive multiculturalism through diverse

narratives. These stories, embedded by participating ceramic artists into their works, were not just seen but experienced through tactile and sensory dimensions enhanced by digital connections [3].

This paper focuses on the development of 'digital connection,' highlighting its crucial role as new ways to add layers of stories and enhance audience engagement. It draws on the author's creative and technical contributions to reimagine and connect these narratives with ceramic stories of Sebastian Conti and Casey Chen's series of ceramic objects. Throughout the development of 'Digital Connection', this paper proposes technologies offer new ways to present art that can transform audience engagement, allowing viewers to interact with and explore the artworks in a more meaningful way.

2 THE FOLDED PLAY: EXPLORING THE

INTERPLAY OF GEOMETRY, ANIMATION, AND INTERACTION

Figure 1: Sebastian Conti's Ceramic objects (Left) and Interactive Animation work developed by June Kim (Right): ADC exhibition view. 2023 Photo: Amy Piddington.

Using ceramics as a sculptural language, Sebastian Conti blends the joys of creative play with the precision of sacred geometry. His artistic practices convey 'observed' and 'abandoned' of the rule of patterning. The resulting ambiguity questions us his work as either an architecture or idol. The inspiration of the classic Indian architectural system of Vāstu behind Conti's artistic practice also

amplifies the connection between the sculptures, object, and room (architecture) [2].

By interpreting Conti's ceramic art practice through Deleuze's concept of the Fold [5], the development of 'digital connection' seeks to convey the dynamic interplay of folding and unfolding. This approach visualizes characteristics and atmospheres that seem alive, inviting us to enter and experience them.

The initial conceptualization of characteristics aimed to view Conti's artifacts more as idols than as architectural objects. The interplay of colors, geometric shapes, and volumes in each piece inspired me to imagine and materialize playful traits. Instead of *personating* [9] the characters to mimic human actions like blinking, jumping, and walking from an animistic perspective, this work utilized a kaleidoscopic animation style. This approach mechanically unfolds, mutates, and intertwines the colors and shapes of each object, thereby representing their playful traits utterly. Furthermore, this mechanical representation continuously explores the ambiguity of architecture or idol that was originally implied in the body of work.

Figure 2: Development of "stopping on movement" in Max MSP. Photo: June Kim.

While the animation represents the fold to express its characteristics seamlessly, it incorporates a system for "stopping on movement"[4], which opens up a sense of thinking or feeling within the animation. Spectators interact by touching the sensor, as seen in Figure 2 above, disrupting the flow to create moments of "deamination" or "inanimation"[9]. This action not only momentarily stops the movement but also adds a jittering effect, which can be interpreted as a layer of provoke by the spectator.

Figure 3 showcases the final setup of the screen-based interactive installation. It features three series of seamlessly looping kaleidoscopic animations on the screen connecting with the sensor-based instruments designed to stop the movement to think and feel.

Figure 3: A Final Set Up. Ceramic Stories [digital connections]. ADC exhibition view. 2023. Photo: Amy Piddington.

As seen in Figure 4, spectators interact with the on-screen animation by pressing the miniature ceramic objects. These miniatures of Conti's work provide a tactile experience, allowing audiences to break the convention of viewing art solely in a gallery setting. In addition, this approach allows spectators to interact with the hidden layers and characteristics of each ceramic piece, represented as a series of digital kaleidoscopic animations.

This installation is thoughtfully built on philosophical and theoretical frameworks while offering playful interaction to audiences. Additionally, the innovative method employed provides a unique and engaging way to experience ceramic artworks in a gallery setting.

Figure 4: A spectator (Left) and Sebastian Conti (Right) interacting with the installation. ADC exhibition view. 2023. Photo: Amy Piddington.

3 FUSING TRADITION AND TECHNOLOGY

Figure 5: Casey Chen's Ceramic works (front) and prints to reanimate built by June Kim (Mounted on wall). ADC exhibition view. 2023. Photo: Amy Piddington.

Blending childhood nostalgia, Casey Chen's ceramics practice draws on historical illustrations from a diverse mix of folklore, mythology, and pop culture. Chen's meticulously hand-thrown pieces convey a unique blend of traditional and contemporary perspectives and ideas [8].

Two inspirations I drew from Casey's work are: 1) the concept of Fusion, which involves blending potentially clashing cultures in a way that allows them to coexist naturally, and 2) the intricate illustrations and meticulously crafted patterns on his ceramic pieces. Building on these principles, I see an opportunity to create

Figure 6: Spectators trying AR feature. Photo: Amy Piddington.

visual narratives that achieve a cohesive aesthetic experience through synthesis.

Drawing from my childhood imagination about a world on the other side of murals where characters could come alive and move (or potentially trapped in), I envisioned to *aminare* (Latin origin of Animate: 'to give life to' or 'to make alive') to Casey's intricately illustrated characters drawn on his ceramics the other side of the world, 'augmented space'[6].

As shown in Figure 6, printed in the format of Chinese scroll painting, chosen elements are arranged in the manner of a British teaware design in terms of creating a new layer of synthesis. By employing the image recognition Augment Reality (AR) technology, layers of butterflies flapping and roam around appears [7]. By pointing out butterflies spectators will experience of *animare* as if they give life to those butterflies. Core part of development process are 1) digitising hand drawn butterflies 2) Animate sequences of butterflies 3) Choose AR platform and apply animated sequences 4) Code to define image targets 5) Repeat of Test and Update.

4 Digital Connection

The development of a "digital connection" was initially proposed to offer new ways of experiencing a series of ceramic objects displayed in a gallery format that limits interaction. Increasingly, museums and exhibits feature interactive artworks that audiences are encouraged to engage with, often supplemented by digital aids to enhance understanding. My contribution to the development of this digital connection is particularly intriguing, as it is built upon collaboration with ceramic artists, interpreting their art practice and artifacts from an art practitioner's perspective. By reinterpreting their work using my artistic mediums of animation and interactive, immersive technologies, the digital connection within the exhibition emerged as an independent digital artwork. This approach aligns with McLuhan's concept of transmedia storytelling, commonly seen in popular media, and presents an opportunity to expand art exhibitions in this innovative way.

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All images used in this paper and videos are either the author's own works or were taken by Amy Piddington and Tony Tran.

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